

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract

This article gives data on the modern methods in the teaching English language.

Key words: methodology, innovation, foreign language, translation method, comparative method, mixed method, ESES project, intellectual games.

Introduction. Currently, a lot is being done to develop education. In particular, foreign language teaching is becoming one of the main tasks for the state. Because it is not for nothing that knowing the language opens the way to knowing the people. In addition, the new FSES and the national education project show the need to improve the organization of the educational process, the introduction of new technologies and methods and techniques of teaching, to increase the interest of schoolchildren in learning to achieve the set goals. . The formation of universal educational activity is the main task of education. The student should be encouraged to continue studying throughout life. And, teachers need to organize their learning activities in a way that doesn't want to distract the student. Active teaching techniques can help the teacher in this.

Active teaching methods not only help to encourage students to think actively and practice in the learning process, but also help to form a positive teaching motivation, reveal and develop creative abilities, help to master the learning material with high efficiency will give.

The development of modern education has led to a new direction of innovative pedagogy. Innovative - means "introduction (dissemination) of news" in English. The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by American researcher E. Rodgers. It is safe to say that the widespread use of advanced, modern and innovative technologies in the field of education has opened the door to great opportunities and goals for young people learning a foreign language. There is nothing in the world that does not develop, and foreign languages are no exception. On the one hand, language as a social phenomenon and system is constantly evolving, and on the other hand, the science that studies this phenomenon is advancing by leaps and bounds. World language - English is developing rapidly. Now there are more and more learners, which means that

many teachers and methods are needed to teach this language. If you are a teacher and armed with methodology, it will be easier to learn English.

Literature review

Demand for English is currently very high. Therefore, a lot of attention is paid to the teaching of this language. As the demand for this language grows, many manuals and technologies are being developed to teach English to students.

Now I have used such manuals. For example, Bozovich A.I. Attitudes of schoolchildren to reading as a mental problem. (/ Bozovich A.I. // Izv. APSFSR.-M., 1986. 36C). This literature contains facts about the mental state of students. This book is very important for teachers. If the teacher knows the mood of the students, he will approach them accordingly. Then they will achieve their goal. They can use appropriate methods and technologies.

The next is "Playing as a Learning Tool for Young Schoolchildren: The Method, Spending". - Novokuznetsk: Ed. Npk, 1998 -c 123. In this literature there are games for school students to learn the language. It is interesting to learn a language through play. Especially schoolchildren get bored quickly and want to change the environment. Such games help students to overcome fatigue and boredom. Another publication, Jalolov English Teaching Methods, Teacher Publishing House. Tashkent ". This book, which includes methods of teaching English, is a great guide for teachers. It is easier to learn a language using these methods. I think that Jalolov also did this with this intention and achieved it.

The main part Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be practiced in the natural environment, ie in the family, in the community or in an organized way. Knowledge of linguistic phenomena is taught theoretically. In this age of international relations, language skills are especially important for multilingualism. In the past, our ancestors mastered 100 languages and spoke them. Now that we know two languages, we are envious. Why did the former learn? How did they achieve this result. It depends, of course, on professional teachers and coaches. Their knowledge and style are overwhelming. Nowadays, the number of people who consider themselves teachers in parentheses has increased. You can say that we can learn the language ourselves. And for some as a baby gets older, he or she will outgrow this. Having a second language is a great way to compare. If you know your native language grammar, vocabulary, the learning process will accelerate. For example, times, the structure of speech, everything goes by this comparison. Your teacher will explain it to you in his own way, comparing it with your own language.

Foreign language and English It is the language of a foreign country. Western European languages (Spanish, English, German, French) and Eastern languages (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Indian) are taught in our country. These languages are included in the curricula of educational institutions. Our native language is learned in a natural environment, and a foreign language in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language takes place mainly in the classroom under the guidance of a teacher. This, in turn, requires the use of appropriate teaching technology. By carefully mastering the achievements of the methodical science, the foreign language teacher achieves a clear understanding of the norms of language experience of the student and its further improvement. Effective teaching of foreign languages requires knowledge of its methods.

As for the fact that the second language is learned in an artificial environment. You can find and learn the right foreign language for yourself as a teacher and sheik, or you can go abroad and learn it faster. If you want to make learning a second language easier, create a 24-hour artificial environment for yourself. Then it is difficult to read and learning is faster. You will achieve this result if you learn each new word and communicate more with your friends. Hop we learned how to learn faster. Now let's talk about effective vca faster learning. Methods really help us. Methodologies are our weapons. With methodologies we achieve what we think. What we learn with them is effective and accelerates. We talked more about the foreign language, but I did not mention English as a second language, as it is one of these languages. But the methods we want to learn will also help us to learn this language, of course. Now let's look at one of the short methods. (1)

Intensive method It was first formed in the early twentieth century on the basis of the "correct" method. Prof.E.I. According to Gez, "the right method creates a favorable opportunity and basis for intensive foreign language teaching."

Some of the principal aspects of the correct method, such as interest in oral speech, especially the choice of speech situations for dialogic speech, increase students' activity in the classroom, are based on one or another of the modern intensive methods. This is natural, of course, because each new method retains the advantages of the previous method. (2)

This term is widely used as a general theory of teaching in the concept of "method". Didactics interprets the term "method" in the sense of the teacher's and student's way of knowing and creating opportunities. General methods of teaching have been developed for the subjects that teach the basics of science. Taking into account the specifics of the subject, the methodology of teaching a

foreign language is developed. In the methodology of teaching a foreign language, the term "method" has 3 meanings.

First, the methodology is a whole direction in history (translation method, correct method, comparative method, mixed method);

Second, the training system, which is part of the above direction;

Third, the way teachers and students interact. (acquaintance, practice, methods of application). The first in the history of foreign language teaching and the second method is called 'historical' methods, and the third is called 'process expression' methods. All the methods of centuries-old history of foreign language teaching are grouped into the above four categories. Let's take a brief look at these methods.

Translation method This method, as its name implies, is the translation of foreign language materials into our native language. Some teachers still misuse translation methods. For example, interpreting a text is a non-methodological method. It is not forbidden to translate some sentences or one or two parts of the text. The purpose of this process is to teach students how to use a dictionary.

The most common of the "translation methods" are "Grammar - translation method" and "Text - translation method". Only from using both translation methods

educational purpose. A foreign language is learned receptively. Methods of teaching a foreign language have been developed based on the linguistic and psychological knowledge of the time. This method is one of the most relevant and convenient ways to teach a second language. It has therefore been one of our methods of use since history. One of the main modern innovative pedagogical technologies of teaching English is the method.

The correct method The main reason for the origin of the name of the method is that when reading in the correct method, bypassing the native language, it is necessary to establish a direct association between the word of the foreign language and the subject, that is, the connection of ideas. seen. A similar method was used in the teaching of English grammar, which sought to establish a direct link between grammatical meaning and form. It is very difficult to adapt from this network to a second language, but if we do it correctly, learning this language will take much longer.

Two of the most modern forms of the correct method - audioligual and audiovisual methods are the most common.

Mixed method This methodology incorporates the scientific and practical aspects of major methodological areas. Mixed methods appeared in the late XIX

and early XX centuries on the basis of a mixture of translation and correct methods.

Comparative method Its full name is "conscious comparative method". One of its first manifestations is to exercise according to the rules. From the modern point of view, the rule of practical spirit is generalized during the exercise.

We will share some modern methods below. I recommend you to get acquainted with some of them, I would like to emphasize that almost all techniques are mobile and can be used not only in foreign language classes, but also in other disciplines.

1. Organizational stage.

"Carousel" ("Merry Go Round") This technique allows the use of imaginative thinking, memory. The first student takes a card from the teacher and names the associations with that word. The card is passed along the chain until it returns to the teacher. Each student has the opportunity to express their ideas quickly.

Questionnaire ("Question Time") is used at different stages of the session. It will be easier for the student to respond to the classmate than for the teacher, and the rigidity and fear of error will disappear. The technique is effective in working with "weak" students, allowing them to reinforce the material studied and identify gaps in each student. "Surprise" is a method aimed at enhancing mental activity and attracting interest in a lesson topic. Forms the ability to analyze, separate, and shape conflict. The teacher finds a point of view that even well-known facts remain a mystery. Puzzle Time There are many differences in this methodology that are successfully applied at different stages of the lesson. For example: FIND WORDS between a set of letters on a specific topic; The words ADD WORD are given, but the letters are omitted; Solve CROSSWORD by answering questions; Find the word in the puzzles, assemble the picture - read the word on the back.

(3) Tongue-twisting tongue twisting devices This technique is used to practice correct pronunciation. I always wanted kids to learn not only to pronounce this or that sound correctly, but to make it fun. You can use picture cards for a specific sound and create the same rhyme. At first, the teacher says the rhyme very slowly to get acquainted with the pronunciation of the sound. Students then repeat in small semantic groups after the teacher, and clap when they hear a given sound in rhyme. Explains the meaning of words that students do not know. Then the teacher pronounces the rhyme aloud again, and the children repeat. And so 3-4 times.

Example: Whoever laughs last, don't laugh best. - The one who laughs for the last time laughs

Motivation for learning activities The problem situation (question) helps to develop motivation, interest in the topic, communication, learning information, and teaching and organizational skills. 2. The teacher creates a problem situation, directs students to solve it, organizes the search for a solution. Thus, the child becomes his own learning position and as a result new knowledge is formed in him, he learns new ways of acting.

Music section / video The teacher prepares a music fragment, audio recording or video in advance. After listening to a part of the recording or watching a movie, the teacher leads the students through discussion to formulate the specific goals, objectives, or topic of the lesson.

Communication A specific form of communication. It is the interaction between people in a learning environment that takes place in the form of speech. There is an exchange of information between the partners and the relationship between them is regulated. The specificity of educational dialogue is determined by the goals of its participants, the conditions of their interaction. Any such dialogue can easily be directed to the main topic of the lesson. For example, the topic of "Your Day" can be started by the teacher at the door of the classroom with the teacher's questions: Good morning! How do you feel today? What time did you get up this morning? Did you have breakfast this morning? Did you do your homework today? What do you plan to do after classes?

"Guess the Topic" Students are presented with pieces of several puzzles. Find missing pieces from classmates, form groups, and collect puzzles. Students are then asked to guess the lesson topic based on the picture taken. (4)

3. Actualization of knowledge.

"Intellectual Warm-up" ("Magic Ball" or "Snow Ball") At this stage, students "remember" past material. The "Intellectual Warm-up" principle can be used throughout the lesson to develop speaking skills. As a rule, the lexical bases of such exercises are located on the board, especially in the initial stage. The growth of the "snowball" can continue in two directions: as vocabulary increases or as grammar complexity increases. (EXAMPLE: I love reading books \ u003e I love reading e-books. I love reading e-books because they are easy to use.) Working with signal cards This past presentation of material in the form of cards. This method helps to create material and restore students' attention. (5)

Associative line For a specific concept of a topic or lesson, you should write word-associations in the column. The way out is as follows: if the series is relatively accurate and sufficient, give an assignment to create a description using written words; then listen, compare with the dictionary version, you can add new

words to the associative line. Graphic dictation is a great way to enhance vocabulary and creative thinking. The children draw things at the teacher's command, then sign the words on the drawn things.

4. Discover new knowledge. Catch the mistake A universal technique that stimulates students' attention. Analyzing information shapes the ability to apply knowledge in a non-standard situation. The teacher informs the students with unknown errors. Students search for the bug in a group or individually, discuss, advise. Students will be placed at a time interval to continue the discussion."Info-karusel"

A universal technique aimed at arousing interest in a lesson topic. Information materials related to the course topic are placed in different tables. The class is divided into small groups depending on the number of tables. Each group reads the information on their desk and completes the assigned tasks. At the end of the allotted time, each group completes the work at their desk and moves on to the other. The groups work until each visits to each data sheet. In addition to the information, there are blank sheets on the tables where small groups write their thoughts. Recreational students understand the new information they have received with the previous one, using the knowledge they have acquired during the comprehension phase. They select the most important information to understand the essence of the topic being studied. Express new ideas and information in your own words, maintain cause-effect relationships independently. Students must restore a portion of the text that was intentionally "broken" by the teacher.

"Interesting chain" "Interesting Chain" A universal technique aimed at updating the knowledge of students of lexical units introduced. This methodology shapes the accumulation of memory and vocabulary on a variety of topics. EXAMPLE: Student 1 names a word on a given topic (topic: "qualities", word "kind"); Student 2 repeats the first and adds his own word ("kind" - "beautiful"); the third student names the first student's word, then the second, and adds himself ("kind" - "beautiful" - "smart" ...) and so on. ., if students are able to continue the chain.

"Agree or disagree" This method helps to realize students' knowledge and activate mental activity. This method allows children to be quickly involved in mental activity, and it makes sense to move on to learning the subject of the lesson. Develops the ability to evaluate a situation or facts; data analysis; reflect your opinion. The teacher says a series of words on a given topic. Children are encouraged to express their attitudes during their statements: agree - repeat "+", disagree - correct "-". Example: subject - UK. Teacher: 1. London is the capital of

the United States. Student: No, I don't agree. London is the capital of GB. Teacher:
2. GB's national language is English. Student: Yes, I agree. GB's national language
is English. ... Etc. (6)

5. Joining the knowledge system Identify errors A universal way to activate
student attention. Develops the ability to analyze information; applying
knowledge in a non-standard situation; critical evaluation of the data obtained.

The teacher informs the students with unknown mistakes. The students look
for the mistake in a group or individually, discuss, give advice. When they come to
a certain idea, the group chooses a speaker. The speaker hands the results to the
teacher or announces the task and the result of solving it to the whole class. Set a
time in advance to prevent the discussion from dragging on.

Conclusion. It should be noted that due to independence, teachers can use a
variety of modern methods in the teaching process. Learning a second language
is a multifaceted doctrine, in the process of which a person experiences complex
psychological changes. In particular, a comparison of a native language with a
foreign language occurs. In this process, different teaching methods and
technologies are used. It is necessary to teach a foreign language and be aware of
its methods. There are many such methods. It is only necessary to master and
improve it. This is a very important process for every teacher. If we work on our
methodology, it is clear that our lessons will be meaningful and interesting. There
are many methods for this and they are being tested in practice. It is only
necessary to study and apply it. Then it will be easier to teach and learn. The work
of the teacher and the student is reduced and becomes more effective. We have
discussed such methods with you above. Do you think it's easy to learn English,
but of course you don't know why it's so humanized? You know, our teachers are
language

learns something new about us more agile than we do. If not, then the memory,
the ability to learn is weakened. But their main weapons are not these - methods,
pedagogical methods. Therefore, it is very easy for teachers to improve their
knowledge. Another example: a teacher has a good command of the language, has
a C1 certificate, but the knowledge of his students is not good. You know what it
is. Of course in the methodology. That is why we did not call teachers the main
tool - methodology. Qualification classes are also organized for this reason. New
games, funny cartoons or videos, puzzles are all ways to teach this lesson. (7)

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